

Oral astringency: effect of ageing and role of saliva

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Abstract

Oral astringency is an important sensory characteristic of food and beverages containing polyphenols. However, while polyphenols enriched diet are recommended especially for elderly, astringency perception in elderly people is not documented. The aim of the present work was to evaluate sensitivity to astringency in function of age and saliva (flow and composition). Fifty-four panellists including 30 elderly people (age=75±4.2) and 24 young people (age=29.4±3.8) participated in this study. Astringency was evaluated by 2-Alternative Forced Choice procedure using four tannic acid solutions (from 0.02 g/l to 0.574 g/l). Whole unstimulated saliva was collected for 5 min before and after sensory tests. Each 2-AFC test was done 3 times and evaluation was performed 3 times in three different sessions. Results showed that there was a significant difference in astringency threshold between young group and elderly group (elderly=0.41 g/l ± 0.23, young=0.29g/l ± 0.26; p=0.011). There were no significant differences in unstimulated salivary flow either at the beginning (p=0.56) or the end (p=0.1) of the session between young and elderly. Moreover, correlation between unstimulated salivary flow and threshold was significant only for young group (r=-0.44, p=0.029).

Keywords: elderly, young, astringency, flow rate, threshold

Introduction

Dietary polyphenols are a class of compounds present in some foods and beverages such as vegetables, nuts, unripe fruits, wine and tea [1]. They are of great interest for the food industry because of their potential beneficial effects on health in particular for the ageing population [2]. In food and beverages, polyphenols, especially tannins, can elicit astringency that is perceived as a quality parameter and desired in balanced levels [3]. On the contrary, above a certain intensity, astringency is usually described as a non-pleasant oral sensation [4], limiting the use and promotion of polyphenols at moderate level in food despite their benefits for health [5]. Several mechanisms have been proposed for the astringency onset but recent results indicate that it most probably relies on the interactions of tannins with the mucosal pellicle [4], causing the aggregation of this thin layer of salivary proteins anchored at the surface of oral mucosa via their interaction with MUC1, a transmembrane protein [6]. This aggregation has been correlated to an increase of the friction forces at the surface of the epithelial cell. This observation indicates that the mucosal pellicle loses its lubricating properties during the aggregation process. In this hypothesis, astringency can be modulated by the presence in saliva of proline-rich proteins (PRPs). Indeed, PRPs, which are secreted by the parotid glands, bind and scavenge tannins [7], giving them the ability to protect the mucosal pellicle toward tannin aggregation.

When it comes to the effect of ageing on astringency perception, the literature is quite scarce, despite that ageing is a common main factor that affects flavour perception [8]. Therefore, the main objective of this study is to investigate the sensitivity to astringency in function of age and salivary flow. On this purpose, a 2-AFC methodology was applied to estimate astringency sensitivity in young and elderly panels while evaluating salivary flow. Relationships between salivary flow and sensitivity in function of age are discussed.

Experimental

All materials (pectin, bicarbonate, Evian water, sodium chloride, leucine, sucrose, glutamate, lactic acid, tannic acid) used in this experiment were food grade.

Sensory evaluation

Fifty-four panellists including 30 elderly (O) people and 24 young (Y) people were recruited to participate in sensory sessions. Training session was conducted before testing session. First, subjects were asked to evaluate tasting samples (salty, bitter, sweet, umami, sour, astringency) in a fixed order at room temperature in plastic cups coded with random number. Second, subjects were trained for the 2-Alternative Forced Choice (2-AFC) procedure using astringency stimulus to understand perfectly the procedure of the sensory test.

At the beginning of each testing session, panellists were asked to taste model tannic acid solution of 1.76 g/L to be well aware of astringency. Astringency threshold was evaluated by a 2-AFC procedure with ascending concentrations (0.02, 0.062, 0.188, 0.574 mg/mL) of tannic acid as described above in material section. In each

2-AFC presentation, two samples were presented: one is aimed sample, one is control. Each 2-AFC test was done 3 times and evaluation was performed 3 times in three different sessions. The testing procedure started from the lowest concentration. Panellists were given the reference or stimulus sample. They were asked to put the samples into their mouth, swirled it gently around the mouth for 30s then spit it. They rinsed mouth with pectin and waited for 1 min before evaluating the second sample. After one additional minute, the panellists were asked to indicate which sample was perceived as astringent. Then, panellists rinsed their mouth with pectin, bicarbonate and Evian water before performing another 2-AFC test.

The sensitivity level is reached when three correct answers from the same concentration are achieved. The best estimate threshold for each subject was evaluated as the geometric mean of the three correct answered concentration and the previous lower concentration. When subjects identified correctly the lowest concentration (0.02 g/l), the geometric mean was calculated between this concentration and the theoretical concentration below, i.e. $0.02/3.05=0.0065$ g/l. On the opposite, when subjects did not identify correctly the highest concentration (0.574 g/l), the geometric mean was calculated between this concentration and the theoretical concentration above, i.e. $0.574*3.05=1.75$ g/l.

Saliva collection

Whole saliva was collected after panellists had rinsed their mouths with pectin 0.1%, bicarbonate 1% and water for 5 min at the start (SFStart) and at the end (SFEnd) of the session. After collection, the tubes were weighted and then stored at -80 °C. Flow rates were determined gravimetrically and expressed as gram per minute (ml/min).

Statistical analysis

Non-parametric analyses were conducted. Mann-Whitney U tests were performed to evaluate differences between Y and O subjects regarding sensory and salivary parameters. Wilcoxon test were performed to evaluate differences between SFStart and SFEnd. Friedman Anova analysis was conducted on threshold and salivary flux measurements to evaluate differences between the three sessions. Spearman rank order correlations were performed for the whole group and within each group (Y and O) to evaluate relationships between salivary and sensory parameters. The significance was set at $p < 0.05$. These tests were done using Statistica® version 13.5.0.17, 1984-2018 TIBCO Software Inc.

Results and discussion

No significant differences were observed between sessions regarding SFStart and SFEnd for both groups, Y (SFStart: Friedman $\chi^2=0.75$, $p=0.68$; SFEnd: Friedman $\chi^2=0.75$, $p=0.68$) and O (SFStart: Friedman $\chi^2=5.2$, $p=0.07$; SFEnd: Friedman $\chi^2=1.3$, $p=0.53$). For this reason, we decided to merge both variables in a unique variable, i.e. mean salivary flow (SF). With regard to the comparison of salivary flow rate, there was no significant difference in SF between Y and O groups ($Z = 1.66$, $p=0.09$) (Table 1).

Table 1: Characteristics of the young and elderly panels

	Y (n=24)				O (n=30)			
	Mean	Median	Range	SD	Mean	Median	Range	SD
Age (years)	29.4	30	24-35	3.8	75	73.5	70-87	4.23
SFStart (ml/min)	0.47	0.47	0.26-0.73	0.14	0.44	0.36	0.23-1	0.24
SFEnd (ml/min)	0.51	0.45	0.23-1.03	0.21	0.41	0.33	0.19-0.91	0.23
SF (ml/min)	0.49	0.47	0.27-0.82	0.16	0.42	0.35	0.11-0.92	0.23
Threshold (g/l)	0.29	0.2	0.04-1.00	0.26	0.41	0.35	0.06-0.78	0.24

No significant differences were observed between the three sessions regarding astringency thresholds for both groups, Y (Friedman $\chi^2=1.13$, $p=0.56$) and O (Friedman $\chi^2=1.14$, $p=0.56$).

A significant difference was observed between Y and O groups ($Z=-2.5$, $P=0.0110$), the O group showing a higher mean astringency threshold than the Y group (Table 1, Figure 1).

Figure 1: Box-plot distributions of threshold values in function of age category (young (Y) and elderly (O)) are shown. The bottom and top of the box correspond to the 25th and 75th percentile, respectively. The horizontal band and the blue diamond correspond to the median and the mean, respectively. The ends of the whiskers represent non-outlier range. X cross correspond to individual data.

Spearman correlation was not significant in whole ($r=-0.16$, $p=0.242$) and O ($r=0.14$, $p=0.47$) group. However, a significant and negative correlation was observed in young (Y) group ($r=-0.44$, $p=0.029$), higher is the salivary flow, lower is the threshold (Figure 2).

Figure 2: correlation between astringency threshold and whole salivary flux observed in the group of young panellists. Plain line corresponds to fitted data. Dotted line corresponds to confidence interval at 95%. X cross correspond to individual data.

Astringency is a complex group of sensations involving drying, roughing and puckering of oral surface, mucosa and muscles around the mouth. To the best of our knowledge, very few researches have investigated sensitivity to astringency in function of age. In this study, it was observed for the first time that astringency threshold was significantly higher in elderly participants than in young participants. In other words, young adults are more sensitive to astringency than elderly adults are. Differences in salivary properties can explain differences regarding taste sensitivity and in particular the flux. Indeed, saliva is present in the oral cavity and constantly bathes the taste buds on the tongue where it can interact with sensory stimulants and play a role in

taste, smell, and chemo-sensation [9]. When it comes to astringency, salivary flow rate has been reported to modulate its perception [10], i.e. subjects with low salivary flow rated astringency higher and recorded longer duration of astringent aftertaste than subjects with high salivary flow. Horne et al. (2002) [11] proposed that there is a negative correlation between resting salivary flow and astringency perceived intensity. Fischer et al. (1994) [12] indicated that the subject group with high salivary flow rate perceived astringency intensity at a significantly lower level than the low flow rate group.

In the present study, this negative relationship was observed significantly for young panel only which is in accordance with studies mentioned previously. However, we did not observe such relationships in the elderly group as well as a difference in salivary flow between Y and O groups, which should explain difference in sensitivity between the two groups. These observations suggest that the role of saliva in astringency sensitivity in function of age should be linked to other salivary parameters, such as its protein composition and, in particular, the level of PRPs.

Conclusion

In summary, the present experiment highlighted the sensory analysis of astringency perception sensitivity in function of age and saliva from a panel formed by 30 elderly people and 24 young people using 2-AFC method with four tannic acid concentrations. This work has demonstrated for the first time that astringency threshold was higher in elderly group than in young group. Concerning salivary flow rate, there were no significant differences between young and elderly groups. However, correlation between salivary flow and threshold was observed only for young individuals suggesting that salivary properties, which influence astringency sensitivity in elderly, are different.

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